

grains better. 3) The amount of nitrogen applied is not excessive. Too much nitrogen leads to excessive vegetative growth, droopy leaves, lodging, increased disease and insect damage, and reduced availability of carbohydrates for grain-filling.

The number of secondary branches and spikelets increased by 11.5-19.0% when nitrogen was applied at the primordial panicle stage. Thus proper nitrogen application may increase the number of filled grains per panicle. It

increased dry panicle weight by 13.0-18.0%.

Use of nitrogen increased the respiratory intensity of primordial panicles by 0.004-0.040 mg CG /g panicle per hour, perhaps because treated plants grow stronger than untreated plants.

The total nitrogen content in the leaf blade was increased by 0.27-1.0% with nitrogen application. That increased photosynthetic activity and photosynthetic products, resulting in more normal branches and spikelets and thus

higher grain yield.

The contents of starch and sugars accumulated in the leaf sheath and stem of the treated plant were higher (about 14.1% and 17.4%, respectively) than in the control plants. Such assimilated carbohydrates contribute to the primordial panicle and thus increase grain yields.

Experiments using ^{14}C and ^{32}P show that the assimilation of ^{14}C and ^{32}P distributed among the middle and the lower parts of the developed panicle spikelets increased yields (Table 2). ■

Increased productivity in rice through inhibition of photorespiration

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Rice, a photorespiring plant (C3-type), loses much of its yield through photorespiration. Treatments with some inhibitors of photorespiration may increase the yield of this crop. In an experiment to test this hypothesis, neutralized aqueous solutions (10^{-3}M) of three photorespiratory inhibitors — isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH), sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO_3), and L-glutamic acid — were foliarly sprayed on the rice variety NC1281 at preflowering and postflowering stages and yield parameters were recorded. The yield parameters included fertility percentage, sterility percentage, grain weight per plant, thousand-grain weight, and grain-straw ratio.

Photorespiratory inhibitors applied at either the preflowering or postflowering stage markedly improved yield parameters and yield per plant (see table). The postflowering treatments showed better effects on yield parameters than the pre-

Effects of photorespiratory inhibitors on some yield parameters and yield of rice (NC1281), West Bengal, India.

Treatment (10^{-3}M)	Ripened grains (%)	Sterile grains (%)	Grain wt ^a (g/plant)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Grain-straw ratio
<i>Preflowering stage (145 days after sowing)</i>					
Control	86.27	13.73	16.20	26.49	0.345
INH	86.54	13.46	20.50 (+ 26.5)	26.52	0.357
NaHCO_3	87.22	12.78	17.30 (+ 6.8)	26.53	0.389
L-glutamic acid	85.38	14.62	16.00 (- 1.2)	26.45	0.340
<i>Postflowering stage (157 days after sowing)</i>					
INH	88.29	11.71	22.10 (+ 36.4)	26.55	0.452
NaHCO_3	87.32	12.68	21.00 (+ 29.6)	26.45	0.378
L-glutamic acid	86.43	13.57	20.00 (+ 23.4)	26.44	0.299

^aFigures within parentheses indicate percentage increases (+) or decreases (-) in yield in relation to the control.

flowering treatments and increased yield per plant considerably over the control. Among the inhibitors used, INH (inhibitor of glycolate pathway) was the most effective; it was followed by NaHCO_3 (inhibitor of RuBP carboxylase-oxygenase). L-glutamic acid (inhibitor of glycolate pathway), when applied at preflowering stage, slightly inhibited yield, but when applied at postflowering stage, significantly increased yield and other

yield parameters. The increase in yield could be ascribed to increased ripened grains and lower sterility. Thousand-grain weight of treated plants did not, however, vary distinctly from the control. The grain-straw ratio was positively correlated with grain weight per plant. Thus, some suitable photorespiratory inhibitors applied at a particular developmental stage of the plant could increase rice yield significantly. ■

A simple method for studying temperature and relative humidity within the rice plant canopy

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The conventional hygrothermograph measures the temperature-humidity levels in a given field, but not the actual microclimate between the tillers and areas where propagules of disease or insect pest organisms begin to develop. Equipment to measure such *microenvironmental* climates exists, but is difficult

to procure and unsafe in most Asian fields.

We have tested a simple system to measure the atmospheric moisture and temperature between tillers of rice clumps with several replications. A weighing bottle with 1 ml of concentrated H_2SO_4 (AR) is weighed with its

cap on, then is fixed to the tiller site by means of a tape and pole. The cap is then removed. A thermometer is fixed similarly. Any number of such bottles and thermometers can be kept at vantage points to get an average estimate of the humidity and temperature at a given area. The bottles are stoppered and reweighed after specific time periods. The difference in weights is the actual amount of moisture absorbed from that environment.

The technique has been used in measuring the temperature and moisture levels in the area surrounding a crop of HR12 (a tall, low-tillering variety) and IET1444 (a semidwarf, high-tillering variety).

Microclimate in tall (HR12) and semidwarf (IET1444) rice varieties. AICRIP, Hyderabad, India.

	Av temperature (°C)		Av atmospheric humidity (g)	
	Near outer tillers	Near inner tillers	Near outer tillers	Near inner tillers
<i>HR12</i>				
Around plot	32.58	31.25	0.020	0.025
Within plot	30.92	29.75	0.023	0.032
<i>IET1444</i>				
Around plot	31.00	29.83	0.020	0.023
Within plot	29.92	28.83	0.020	0.024

Trend in temperature and humidity fluctuations (variety: IET4141), Hyderabad, India.

ity). Statistically the data were highly significant (see table).

The figure shows the temperature and moisture levels of another semidwarf, IET4141, recorded over a 2-day period.

The method is simple and useful in categorizing the moisture-temperature relationships in restricted areas within a

plant canopy to explain pest buildup. Further studies on the relationship between microclimate and the buildup of brown planthoppers and fungal pathogens in high-tillering semidwarf varieties with dense canopies are under way. ■

Effect of low temperature and low light intensity on the heading stage and flowering of indica rice

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Rice plants in southern China are sometimes damaged at the heading stage by low temperature and low light intensity in autumn. Thus, the sterility of late-season rice varieties caused by cold temperature can be an important constraint to rice production.

We examined the effect of cold temperature and low light on the physiological characters of rice anthers and flowers, and on the distribution or assimilation of ¹⁴C and ³²P in rice organs. Our objective was to identify

agronomic practices that prevent cold injury in rice cultivation.

A low night temperature of 12° C and a high day temperature of 22° C were maintained in artificial light cabinets. Light intensity was maintained at about 2,000 lx and relative humidity from 71 to 83%.

The respiratory intensity of rice plant florets decreased by 7.5% and that of anthers decreased by 25% after 24 hours of cold temperature and low light treatment. It decreased by 36.1% and 81.2% in the 48-hour treatment, and by 30.6% and 75.0% in the 106-hour treatment. Thus, prolongation of cold temperature and low light intensity seriously damaged the anthers.

In the first experiment with ¹⁴C (Table 1) the ¹⁴C values (counts per minute [cpm]/50 mg) and the total ¹⁴C values

differed markedly. The control flag leaf contained 4,497 cpm/ 50 mg and a total of 18,263 cpm; the treated flag leaf had 6,309 cpm/ 50 mg and a total of 23,953 cpm. Cold temperature and low light impeded the translocation of photosynthetic products of ¹⁴C from the flag leaf to the other organs and decreased their exported percentage. But the total ¹⁴C content (1 29,697 cpm) of treated plants was less than that of the control plants (377,471 cpm). The total ¹⁴C contents decreased in organs other than the flag leaf. In treated roots, it decreased even more (treated roots, 44 cpm/ 50 mg and 712 total cpm; control roots, 9,999 cpm/ 50 mg and 157,369 total cpm). Thus the roots injured by cold temperature and low light were famished and received less energy. On the other hand, cold temperature and low light